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Focus At Play: Exploring Gamification through A Case Study Of Narrative-Based Focus Apps

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ABSTRACT

"Focus apps" are a popular solution to minimise the distractions and temptations of smartphones and online content, based on the contradictory premise of using a mobile application to contrast smartphone addiction. These applications typically deploy several gamification strategies, often with a strong orientation towards narrative and storytelling. In this paper, we investigate how gamification is implemented in such apps and how users perceive its effectiveness in terms of enhanced focus, by analyzing three cases: *Focus Quest*, *Forest*, and *Study Bunny*. We first make use of a taxonomy of gamification to highlight the different strategies adopted: while all three apps apply gamification and narrative-based strategies to help users focus on tasks, their design approaches vary significantly. We then complement the investigation by examining online reviews on Google Play to reconstruct users' accounts of perceived app efficacy. A content analysis of the reviews showcases how the strategies of the different apps result in diverse outcomes in users' feelings towards the apps, ranging from positive to negative, and perception towards the effectiveness of gamification strategies, both effective and ineffective. Our results suggest that, to harness the potential of gamification in focus apps, the balance between gamification and the focus-enhancing goals, potential ethical implications, the strategic use of story-based strategies, and the technological aspect of online apps should be carefully considered. In this sense, we argue that the concept of using gamified apps to combat mobile device overuse presents an inherent paradox and raises ethical concerns about addiction and commercial exploitation. This raises

the question of whether gamification is the best tool for the focus-enhancing purpose, which should be further investigated.

CCS CONCEPTS

• **Human-centered computing** → **Empirical studies in HCI**.

KEYWORDS

Gamification, Focus Apps, Story-based strategies, Storytelling, User Experiences

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1 INTRODUCTION

The interstitial nature of smart devices causes our daily lives to be filled by all sorts of digital stimuli fostering ever-growing demands for our attention [64]. Such trend is expected to continue towards the future of the connected society, powered by high-performance communication infrastructure [29, 60, 61], where digital media consumption has been normalized. However, several studies indicate that the continuous growth of digital lifestyles has a significant impact on the shrinking attention spans of humans [16, 28, 59]. The massive amount of online content we encounter daily across multiple media sources encourages divided attention and media multitasking, which is closely associated with attention lapses [18]. This phenomenon can lead to negative consequences in different aspects of lives, such as in academic achievement, mental health, and social interaction [16]. In the educational setting, excessive uses of smartphones and Internet are related to addiction and procrastination, resulting in low academic performance [4, 22]. Additionally, studies have shown a connection between intense digital media use and mental health issues, such as

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depression and social anxiety [13, 18, 32]. Furthermore, a research by Romer et al. [56] shows that heavy Internet use among youth is linked to their social withdrawal from, for example, sports and clubs.

As maintaining focus on our tasks becomes increasingly challenging and presents potential problems that affect our daily lives, several mobile applications have been developed that offer to aid with focus. These "focus applications", are designed to enhance the ability to concentrate and stay focused and consequently support productivity. Aligned with the popularity of gamification in promoting behavior change [11], such apps often incorporate various game-like, gameful or gamified strategies and features, such as points and challenges, to assist users in resisting digital distractions. The examples of gamified focus apps in the market are Forest, Habitica, Study Bunny, Focus Quest, and Bounty Tasker.

Within the many behaviour change interventions focusing on wellness, mental and physical health [2, 6, 46], several authors engage explicitly gamification strategies in mobile health [23, 26]. There is, however, a gap when it comes to gamified behaviour change interventions that aim at increasing focus and productivity. Particularly, the potential of approaches such as narratives, as part of gamification, have not been fully explored in this area [39]. Furthermore, the implementation of gamification in focus apps raises an interesting paradox that requires further exploration: the encouragement to use a digital mobile app to help curb digital mobile apps' usage. In other words, while focus apps aim to reduce digital distractions and provide a controlled digital environment suitable for focused work or study, they makes use of gamification's ability to increase user engagement with the app to achieve the stated goal [66]. This incongruity fosters us to reconsider how to apply gamification in different contexts more effectively, particularly in the context of focus apps. We, therefore, consider that exploring and mapping this specific segment, with particular attention to gamification strategies, would be a worthwhile endeavour. In this regard, this paper aims to be an initial step, as currently there is limited knowledge on the application of gamification on focus applications and its effectiveness [23, 40].

In this paper, we aim to investigate the gamification strategies that are utilized in focus apps, and their users' perceived effectiveness in terms of fostering focus, to gain a better understanding of the extent to which gamification is beneficial for this application. We approach this phenomenon through two research questions: *How do focus applications utilize gamification?* and *How do users evaluate its effect?* We provide an answer to these questions through the analysis of three popular focus applications, *Focus Quest*, *Forest*, and *Study Bunny*. For each of these cases we investigate how gamification is deployed, and what strategies are able to affect user experience. Among different gamification strategies, we are especially interested in the use of story-based strategies – and the experiences it can afford in users – as part of gamification. All our cases feature narrative elements as key components, and narratives have been indicated as crucial elements to facilitate focus [40, 63]. To complement our analysis of gamification strategies and examine how users describe their perception of their efficacy, we make use of content analysis of online user feedback. This twofold approach should allow us to enhance our understanding of how focus applications utilize

gamification and how is it evaluated by users in terms of their sense of focus, as well as to define possible areas of improvement for future designers and practitioners.

2 BACKGROUND

2.1 Gamification and gamification design taxonomies

Today, gamification is largely understood as the implementation of game design strategies to non-game environments, such as business, education, marketing, self-care, or any activity where user engagement is desired, to afford similar experiences that games typically do [30, 62]. These strategies, which aim to facilitate gameful experiences, often serve as motivational incentives, such as through providing points, challenges or visualizing progress to further facilitate psychological outcomes of, for example, enjoyment, curiosity or sense of flow for end users [35, 44]. These psychological outcomes can act as mediators for behavioral changes in terms of improved performance, efficiency or motivation [35, 57], depending on the intended outcome of the service or activity.

In order to deploy gamification effectively, it is essential to design and choose appropriate collection of gamification strategies that align both with users' as well as designers' objectives. To achieve this, one option is to utilize existing frameworks and schemes of gamification, and explore how to use them effectively (see e.g., [10, 47]). Over the years, more than 50 frameworks have been introduced in the literature [10, 47], however, only a few focus on learning in different contexts, and majority of them have been criticized for being too generic or not validated empirically [63]. In this study, we utilize a taxonomy by Toda et al. [63] for its hierarchical structure and detailed support provided for designers and developers. It categorizes gamification into five dimensions: (1) performance and measurement (e.g., badges, achievements, levels, progression, points, and stats, that are used to provide feedback to users), (2) ecological elements (e.g., randomness, imposed choice, time pressure, limited items or collections, and marketplaces, which are used to create interactions with users) (3) social elements (e.g., competition, cooperation, reputation or status, and social pressure, which enhance the interaction between users), (4) personal elements (e.g., surprise or new game content, missions, side-quests and challenges, which create meaningful experiences and motivate users), and finally, (5) fictional elements (e.g., narrative and storytelling that aim in creating a cohesive and immersive context and environment that users can meaningfully engage in). While the proposed taxonomy is considered appropriate for evaluating especially gameful educational contexts, it has its shortcomings in terms of, for example, providing explicit psychological and behavioral changes that correspond to each dimension [38]. Relating to this paper's topic of focus apps, especially the dimension of "Fictional" can be argued to be limited in capturing the intricate nature of narratives that are in the centre of facilitating user engagement and focus, also within gamified applications [63].

Aligned with Toda et al. [63], we interpret narratives and storytelling as part of gamification strategies. Narrative refers to the sequence of events in the user experience, shaped by their choices and actions [63]. Storytelling, on the other hand, is how the story is

conveyed, such as through text, voice, and other sensory elements, to enhance the narrative within a specific experience [63, 67], which is considered an important technique for facilitating learning and understanding [65, 67]. In order to craft a compelling story for the user, a variety of design strategies are used to integrate the concept of experience into narratives and convey them through different storytelling techniques [67]. In this sense, we depict this approach as a story-based strategy [20] to provide a better understanding of the employment of fictional elements in gamified experiences. However, within the gamification field, debates exist around the relationship between games and stories, and whether, for example, plots or narrative developments should be considered separately as its own concept [7]. While arguments can be made for both sides, research shows rather unanimously that fictional elements typically associated with stories can play a vital role in gamification efforts by adding meaning and emotional resonance to gamified experiences [8, 24].

2.2 Focus applications and gamification

The increasing reliance on smart technologies in daily activities makes it so that people are constantly bombarded with notifications, tempting apps, and endless feeds of content – which steadily diminishes our capacity for sustained focus [64]. Simultaneously, people are increasingly dissatisfied with the amount of time they spend on their smartphones, partly due to applications' and their algorithms' design to keep users addicted and constantly checking their phones [15, 19]. To tackle the issues of excessive smartphone usage that hinders other productivity, the app market has started to offer mobile apps that promise enhanced focus and concentration for their users. These apps have come to be known as "focus apps". Most commonly, such apps use goal setting, website and app blocking, timer setting, and self-tracking as their main features to assist the user in reducing mobile phone use [51, 52]. However, while the term "focus apps" is widely used in the industry, a comprehensive definition supported by rigorous research remains in its infancy. Existing definitions often stem from Internet resources like developer blogs [48, 51]. Furthermore, the term has been currently used interchangeably with "productivity apps" or "digital detox apps", leading to potential confusion. Even though focus apps share some overlapping features with these two app types (e.g., timers and web blockers), we propose that they all have a distinct emphasis. In productivity apps, the main content considers task management and work efficiency [9], which have a broader scope compared to focus apps. Then again digital detox apps target overall screen time reduction [1], aiming mainly for encouraging users to reduce mobile device use. Noteworthy, focus apps share some similarity with a subset of mobile health and lifestyle apps that similarly undertake behaviour change in a wide variety of interventions, ranging from treatments of eating disorders, encouraging physical activity, improving sleep or promoting mental health and wellness. While mobile health and lifestyle apps have been studied to a greater extent [1, 6, 42], solely focus apps have not received much attention. Therefore, to address this ambiguity, this paper defines focus apps as "mobile applications designed to help users concentrate on their tasks by reducing distractions and fostering a more structured work routine".

Previous studies suggest that employing a mobile app as a strategy to limit phone use can be effective [52]. User motivation and self-awareness have been deemed critical in managing to reduce this behavior [52]. App designers are increasingly implementing various gameful, playful and story-based features in focus apps, probably to enhance the persuasiveness of the apps and support users in reaching their objectives. Prior literature [17, 40, 43, 52] investigates the implementation of gamification strategies in mobile apps aiming to help users to avoid using their phone. For example, one feature to restrict phone usage are rewards and punishments, including gamification strategies like point collection, leader boards, and achievements [43]. Moreover, the study from Bychkov and Young [17] indicates that gamification is one of the behavior change methods used to enhance the effectiveness of apps aiming to curb smartphone addiction. A study by Kirchner-Krath et al. [40] found that both gamified and non-gamified focus apps were beneficial, while using a gamified app had particularly positive effects for motivation and self-control of users. Effective features highlighted by the study were focus timer and task planning, as well as enjoyable narrative [40]. Aligned with Kirchner-Krath et al. [40], previous studies state that adapting the app into a user's individual way of working is important for a focus app to be effective, and design of the apps should focus more on this area [52, 68].

However, a study by You and Karlsen [66] point out the risk of using too many interactive elements in an app, which could paradoxically direct the user's attention more towards using the smartphone. Increased engagement in gamified focus apps has also been found to create more distractions that can divert the attention of users, which can be caused by user focusing too much on the gamified elements or gamified elements conflicting with user's goals [25, 40, 68]. This raises concerns about the potential drawback for using gamification in focus apps and introduces questions on the feasibility of engaging users with a smartphone app while simultaneously aiming to reduce their smartphone usage. Additionally, it should be noted that generally these commercial apps have optional in-app purchases directly tied to the gamification elements, which raises concerns about the potential for addiction and irresponsible money use. This goes in line with the work by [54], revealing a significant relationship between in-game purchases, the risk of developing addiction, and overspending issues. Their work points out the potential drawbacks of excessive play leading to financial risk. In this regards, it is imperative to consider developers' underlying motivations when analyzing these apps; are their primary goals genuinely focused on user well-being, or are they driven by maximizing user retention and screen time for commercial purposes? Overall, it is essential to consider the potential of these apps to exploit users.

3 METHODS

This study adopts a critical approach to case study research [27] to examine how gamification is used within narrative-based focus apps in real-world contexts. Case study approach was chosen as it allows a use of multiple data sources and analysis of them convergently, in order to build understanding of the studied phenomenon [12]. The selection of data sources for case studies in human-computer interaction (HCI) research often requires customization to meet the

specific study requirements, such as digital artifacts, activity logs, and email messages [41]. As an initial step towards understanding the phenomenon of gamified focus apps, we chose to use data from applications and user feedback to gain preliminary insights and establish a groundwork for more extensive future investigations. In the following section, a detailed explanation of case study selection, data collection and analysis is provided.

3.1 Case studies

To study the presented research questions of *how do focus applications utilize gamification* and *how do users evaluate its effect?*, three focus applications, *Focus Quest*, *Forest*, and *Study Bunny*, were selected for analysis due to their popularity, availability, and variety in gamification strategies. In terms of popularity, *Study Bunny* has over 5 million downloads on Google Play, *Focus Quest*, recognized as Google Play's best of 2021, for example, in the Thailand, Philippines, Hong Kong, and Taiwan region, and *Forest* leading the productivity apps on the Apple App Store underscores their prevalence (see Table 1 for details). Furthermore, the accessibility of these apps played a role in the selection process, as they are all accessible to Android users, a platform with an overwhelming majority of mobile app users globally [58]. Finally, these apps employ various gamification strategies to prompt different user motivation and engagement, aiming to enhance focus. *Focus Quest* features rich storytelling, including hero training and world-saving quests, to guide user throughout the gamified experience. In contrast, *Forest* and *Study Bunny* offer straightforward narratives about plants and a pet bunny. *Forest* encourages user motivation through the visual growth of planted trees, while *Study Bunny* relies on emotional attachment to its pet character.

Descriptions of selected focus applications The selected focus apps (see Figure 1) are dedicated to help users stay focused. The first chosen app, *Focus Quest*, is a mobile application for increasing focus and productivity developed by Shikudo, released on 11 February 2021. The application adopts the element of a role-playing game (RPG) to gamify users' tasks in everyday life with the primary goal of helping enhance their work productivity and concentration. There are various features, including a focus timer and assistance in task management, where users can engage in challenges across numerous stages and associated rewards.

Secondly, *Forest*, developed by Seekrtech and released on 15 March 2016, aims to help users maintain focus in their daily activities. The app offers a variety of usages customized for different situations, encompassing study, work, entertainment and rest. The primary aim of the app is to grow a virtual plant, which dies if the focus is interrupted, i.e., when the smartphone is used. Additionally, *Forest* collaborates with tree planting organization *Trees for the Future*, letting users plant real trees by earning gold coins in the app, thus bridging virtual and physical worlds.

Thirdly, *Study Bunny* is a focused timer app developed by Superbyte and released on 11 September 2019. The app facilitate users to focus on studying and completing tasks while the timer is running. Users can set the timer for focusing on studying, make to-do lists, and create flashcards to help them study. The app's main feature is a virtual bunny, which displays different emotions based on how much focused time the user completes and gives

encouraging prompts, such as turning the pages of a book happily. Users can purchase virtual items to modify and beautify the bunny and its environment, which visualizes user's progress and the level of use with the app.

Figure 1: Screenshots of the selected apps

3.2 Data collection and analysis

To examine the selected three apps, we scrutinized the utilized gamification strategies by using the gamification taxonomy by Toda et al. [63] as a framework. Additionally, we approach the investigation of the story-based strategies in the selected focus apps through another supplementing framework. After revising various existing models and frameworks (e.g., [3, 5, 8]), we chose to adopt the storytelling element categorization formulated by Zhang and Bowman [67] due to its applicable articulation of story-based strategies that include elements such as: plot, characters, setting, conflict, resolution, dialogue, and point of view. The aim of this approach was to discover the nuanced deployment of gamification and storytelling, and facilitate an understanding of their respective design paradigms.

To ensure consistency in our data collection process, we constructed three app comparison tables (similar to Table 2 and Table 3). Following this, each app was assigned to one researcher for independent analysis, focusing on the identification of gamification strategies. Each of the three researchers then cross-validated the initially completed analyses of the apps to reduce the influence of personal bias and strengthen our interpretation. After completing the independent analysis and cross-validation, researchers proceeded with shared analysis of the apps to ensure uniformity of understanding of the identified gamification strategies.

In addition to analyzing the applications, user reviews were collected to investigate the perceptions of gamification utilized in the focus apps. To collect the user reviews, we chose the Google Play Store as a database since it contains a large number of user interactions and feedback on new versions of apps. We used "exportcomments.com" as an extraction tool to export user reviews from the Google Play Store. In order to get the latest information

Table 1: Details of the applications' reach (Data as at 2 April 2024)

	Rating		Downloads		Reviews		Purchase Price	
	App Store	Google Play	App Store	Google Play	App Store	Google Play	App Store	Google Play
Focus Quest	4.7/5	4.5/5	N/A	500K+	370	4.36K	free	free
Forest	4.8/5	4.7/5	N/A	10M+	40.9K	659K	\$3.99	free
Study Bunny	4.8/5	4.6/5	N/A	5M+	10.7K	50.5K	free	free

from the users using the latest version of the app, we chose to extract the latest reviews for the last year, between 1 April 2023 and 20 April 2024. After excluding 42 reviews that were not in English or contained only emoticons, we obtained 2,014 valid reviews. Of these, 140 reviews were from *Focus Quest*, 1,028 were from *Forest*, and 846 were from *Study Bunny*.

Qualitative content analysis was employed to analyze the user reviews and offer insights into overall perceptions of gamification as well as its perceived effectiveness. Content analysis is an appropriate research method to study written texts or media to reveal relevant symbolic implications and meaningful cultural themes within the studied phenomenon [14]. With content analysis, the findings are constructed directly from data, albeit the procedure is not linear as it is necessary to go back and forth between data and analysis process. The process consists of three stages: reducing, clustering and abstracting the data [45]. With reducing, all irrelevant data is filtered out by coding all frequent expressions, interpretations and schemes guided by the research questions. During this stage, the 2,014 valid comments were examined to identify content related to gamification and opinions towards its effect. To ensure the reliability of the coding process, subsets of user comments were independently coded by the three leading authors. In the clustering stage, these codes were compared, reflected and categorized [45], which resulted in four subcategories (see Table 4). Eventually, in the final analysis stage, abstracting, these categories were sorted into main categories of *emotional expressions* and *perceived effectiveness*, which are further discussed in the following sections.

4 RESULTS

4.1 Gamification strategies in the focus applications

To address the first research question, we identified and compared the gamification used in each app to better understand how it is implemented to achieve the apps' goals. To do so, we adopted the gamification taxonomy by Toda et al. [63] as a framework for the analysis. Table 2 illustrates an overview of each element in the three selected apps, marking its presence with an "x" and absence with a "-". The results show that *Focus Quest* has a strong representation of all elements of the Performance, Personal, and Fictional dimensions. It also includes four elements from the Ecological dimension and one element from the Social dimension. On the other hand, *Forest* has three elements from Performance, Ecological, and Personal dimensions, two elements from Social dimension, and one element from the Fictional dimension. When compared to these two apps, *Study Bunny* includes four elements in

the Performance and Personal dimensions, as well as three elements in the Ecological dimension. It also contains some elements of the Fictional and Social dimensions.

To better understand how story-based strategies were integrated within the gamified apps, a more detailed categorization by Zhang and Bowman [67] was utilized as a framework, which allowed for a more in-depth analysis of the "Fictional" dimension (see Table 3). Table 3 shows that *Focus Quest* adopts all story-based strategies, while *Forest* and *Study Bunny* only include three strategies. The results indicate that all three apps incorporate two common story-based strategies, supporting characters and setting, to engage users. However, the apps differ in how they design the setting, introduce characters, and develop character's interactions within their narratives.

Forest and *Study Bunny* share a common feature in that they both ask users to take care of another being through focused attention. This connection to the character in the apps is established from a third-person *point of view*, framing the users as *protagonist* responsible for the well-being of *supporting characters* appearing in the apps. *Study Bunny* focuses on fostering an affective emotional attachment to the bunny character, which serves as the app's *supporting character*. While *Forest* features plants as *supporting characters*, the forest serves as a visual representation of users' focused time, where users can view their time statistics simultaneously.

On the contrary, *Focus Quest* engages users by creating a *plot* and advancing a character in a storyline. It tells a story about "Focusland" (*Setting*) where the Guardian of Time protects the rule of time so that people in Town can live and work in peace. The *Conflict* of the story is that the Guardian of Time has gone missing, and various monsters (*Antagonists*) start appearing. Users act as main characters (*The first-person point of view*) in the story, where they are given a mission to find their father and the Guardian of Time. The story urges users to take on an adventure to achieve the mission in the game and unfold the story behind all the incidents. At the same time, users can accomplish their daily tasks in real life. There are also a variety of *supporting characters* and different *settings* with aims to make the story richer.

4.2 User feedback on the gamified focus applications

All three examined apps provide various gamification and narrative-based strategies with aims to help with focusing on tasks. However, the design of gamification in each app differs. To gain a bigger picture of the effect of different means to implement gamification and its impact on users, we examined user feedback to determine how users evaluate gamification and how it motivates them to

Table 2: Gamification dimensions identified in the selected focus apps

	Focus Quest	Forest	Study Bunny
1. Performance / Measurement			
1.1 Acknowledgement (badges, medals, trophies, achievement)	x	x	x
1.2 Level (skill level, character level)	x	-	-
1.3 Progression (progress bars, steps, maps)	x	x	x
1.4 Point (scores, experience points, skill points)	x	-	x
1.5 Stats (information, head up display, dashboards)	x	x	x
2. Ecological			
2.1 Chance (randomness, luck, fortune, probability)	x	-	-
2.2 Imposed choice (choice, judgement, paths)	-	-	-
2.3 Economy (transaction, market, exchange)	x	x	x
2.4 Rarity (items, collection, exclusivity)	x	x	x
2.5 Time pressure (countdown timer, clocks)	x	x	x
3. Social			
3.1 Competition (player vs. player, leader boards, scoreboards)	-	-	-
3.2 Cooperation (teamwork, co-op groups)	x	x	x
3.3 Reputation (classification, status, title)	-	x	-
3.4 Social Pressure (peer pressure, guild missions)	-	-	-
4. Personal			
4.1 Novelty (update, surprise, changes)	x	x	x
4.2 Objectives (missions, side-quests, milestones)	x	x	x
4.3 Puzzle (challenges, cognitive tasks, actual puzzles)	x	-	-
4.4 Renovation (boots, extra life, renewal)	x	-	x
4.5 Sensation (visual or sound stimulation)	x	x	x
5. Fictional			
5.1 Narrative (karma system, implicit decision)	x	x	x
5.2 Storytelling (script, text stories, audio queues)	x	-	-

Table 3: Story-based strategies identified in the selected focus apps

	Focus Quest	Forest	Study Bunny
1. Plot	x	-	-
2. Point of view	First-person PoV (Hero)	Third-person PoV (Tree)	Third-person PoV (Bunny)
3. Character			
3.1 Protagonist	x	-	-
3.2 Antagonist	x	-	-
3.3 Supporting characters	x	x	x
4. Setting	x	x	x
5. Conflict	x	-	-
6. Resolution	x	-	-
7. Dialogue	x	-	-

become more focused, thereby addressing the second research question.

The content analysis of user reviews formed two distinct themes emerging from the user feedback: *emotional expressions* and *perceived effectiveness*. The first theme, *emotional expressions*, captures the range of emotions users described when interacting with the apps, spanning from positive feelings like "awesome," "fun", and "relaxing" to negative sentiments such as "worst," "boring", and "annoying." Among the reviews included to the content analysis, the percentages of reviews reflecting positive emotions were as follows: 58.6% for *Focus Quest*, 67.3% for *Forest*, and 87.8% for *Study Bunny*. In contrast, the percentages of reviews reflecting negative emotions were 13.6%, 4.3%, and 2.4%, respectively. The second

theme, *perceived effectiveness*, reflects on the implementation of gamification elements and whether users believe they actually facilitate focus. This feedback was categorized as either effective (with keywords like "productive," "successful", and "helpful") or ineffective (with keywords such as "complicated," "fail", and "error"), which suggests that if, and how, gamification strategies enhance or impede the apps' primary purpose. The share of user reviews referring to effectiveness of the apps was 39.3% for *Focus Quest*, 62.6% for *Forest*, and 31.8% for *Study Bunny*. Meanwhile, 11.4%, 1.8%, and 0.1% of reviews mentioned ineffectiveness of the respective apps. Table 4 details specific keywords associated with each theme. To gain deeper insights, we will examine these results in conjunction with the gamification dimensions identified in the previous section, which will elucidate how the feedback themes relate to gamification embedded within the apps' design.

Within the *emotional expressions* theme, the results indicate that users primarily reflect their feelings directed towards their overall experience with the apps. While some reviews gave only one single word as responses, others provided insights into the specific factors driving those sentiments. We observed that gamification has an impact on user emotion, leading to both positive and negative feelings during the app usage. First, the finding reveals that the Personal dimension, particularly the visual and sound effects of the apps (*Sensation*) can evoke positive emotions and improve their engagement, as shown in the following user reviews:

"[...] It feels fun and refreshing to use the focus timer, the art is adorable, and I love all the tiny UX

Table 4: Key themes extracted from user feedback

Themes	Sub-Themes	Keywords
1. Emotional Expression	1.1 Positive Feelings	Super, Nice, Great, Cool, Awesome, Amazing, Wonderful, Fantasticating, Impressive, Enjoy, Fun, Relaxing, Obsessed, Mind blowing, Phenomenal, Lovely, Cute, Cheerful
	1.2 Negative Feelings	Worst, Hate, Boring, Annoying
2. Perceived Effectiveness	2.1 Effectiveness	Effective, Productive, Helpful, Useful, Successful, Improve, Motivate, Encourage, Concentrate, Be better, Disciplined
	2.2 Ineffectiveness	Problem, Complicated, Don't understand, How to, Why, Unable to, Interrupted, Fail, Error, Glitches

features that you can click on item icons to get a small description of what they are is SO helpful and just a lovely detail. [...]" (28 February 2024, *Focus Quest* Reviews)

"[...] The forest noises that the app provides helps us have a peaceful spirit while studying and prevents us from stressing and not focusing. [...]" (21 August 2023, *Forest* Reviews)

"[...] The bunny is just so adorable, and the whole layout is really aesthetic <3 It's great for a lighthearted bit of fun along with a warm fuzzy feeling that anyone's inner child would absolutely adore. [...]" (18 January 2024, *Study Bunny* Reviews)

Some users expressed negative feelings by reflecting on the Fictional dimension. To illustrate, the large number of dialogues used in *Focus Quest* made some users feel bored or even feel like it is a waste of time (4 December 2023, *Focus Quest* Reviews). In addition to gamification elements, we observed that the Internet connectivity is one of the factors that impacts users' feeling. Based on reviews, users expressed dissatisfaction with the requirement of the constant connection while using the app, leading to a demand for offline versions of the focus apps. Some examples of users' feedback are as follows:

"[...] Doesn't open in offline! At least it must work just for setting focus time.. that's worst! Please.. being online is itself distraction... [...]" (11 September 2023, *Focus Quest* reviews)

"[...] But it need network connectivity (pensive face emoji) that's my only problem as I use a tablet which lives on hotspot connection of my mother's phone and when she is out I won't be able to use this (crying face emoji) But over all Its great!" (7 July 2023, *Study Bunny* reviews)

In this sense, the need for constant wireless connectivity can hinder the gamified aspects of these apps, which has the potential to disrupt user engagement and motivation. Moreover, it can be seen that user feelings are also influenced by how effective they perceive the apps to be. This highlights the importance of app functionality that is not only aesthetically pleasing but also works well in meeting users' needs and expectations.

Examining the second theme of *perceived effectiveness* of the apps, the analysis of reviews indicates that various elements from Performance dimension play a crucial role in motivating users to concentrate more on their tasks. *Forest*'s users described that *Achievement* in planting more trees and seeing them grow is a representation of *Acknowledgement*, which became the primary motivation for using the app for productivity, as one user wrote:

"helps a lot in concentration and I feel a sense of accomplishment after planting and growing a tree. as a procrastinator, this app is a game changer" (27 January 2024, *Forest* Reviews)

Moreover, the illustration of a progress bar (*Progression*) and a personalized dashboard (*Stats*) was indicated to be an effective way of boosting user motivation. One user (19 February 2024, *Forest* Reviews) mentioned that the app offers a summary of past progress and the number of hours spent studying, which helped them to find motivation for studying. In addition, another dimension that enhanced users' productivity were *Points*. One of the reviews stated that the way the app decreases points when users engage in other social media apps encouraged them to stop and focus on studying:

"It really keeps me focused. When I try to open social media I have to pause the time but if I pause the points would be reduced, so I wont pause much and study full fledged." (16 February 2024, *Study Bunny* Reviews)

Unlike the *Forest*'s app, if users go to another app during focus time, the tree they were growing will perish. In this sense, the punishment mechanic is applied as motivation that keeps users focused on their tasks, as shown in the following user review:

"I feel I'm very gently encouraged not to get off track. I don't want my tree to die, so it works, and I'm not irritated by it like other timers. [...]" (17 October 2023, *Forest* Reviews)

However, according to the reviews, one of the most effective gamification dimensions used in *Focus Quest* to promote users' engagement were *Levels*, which was not present in the other two apps. This was incorporated in the form of character levels, which many have credited for keeping them motivated to use the app:

"Phenomenal!! I love it! It made me really want to study for the sake of leveling up my character. It's really motivating, and I don't waste away my day shaming myself for not getting anything done. [...]" (24 March 2024, *Focus Quest* Reviews)

From the Ecological dimension, we observed that all examined apps contain a shop or marketplace to create *Economy* within the gamified environment. This element serves as a trading point where users can come and exchange their focus time with desired in-game accessories or materials related to the main character. The shops in these apps offer various limited items and collections (*Rarity*) for sale. This presumably aims to add a sense of challenge and excitement, which then encourages users to collect their focus time more to get rewarded with coins or diamonds in exchange. According to user reviews of *Forest*, the *TinyTan* event, which was a time-limited event providing special mini BTS (the South Korean boy band) member's character trees, encouraged users' engagement

with the app and motivation to study more to earn coins that can be used to buy the limited trees:

"[...] But I would love it even more if the TinyTan event could come back, because I wasn't able to get them all. I really hope they can come back, and I know some of my friends would love it too, so please bring it back." (27 March 2024, *Forest Reviews*)

Feedback from users also indicates that the higher the price, the greater the motivation it generates. For example, a user of *Forest* praised the concept of high-priced trees, as it required more focused sessions to purchase expensive trees in the game, which was helpful for study sessions (6 January 2024, *Forest reviews*). Likewise, a user of *Study Bunny* mentioned that although the items in the shop are costly, it motivates them to study harder and earn more coins (16 March 2024, *Study Bunny reviews*). However, beyond the potential in enhancing user engagement, it is worth considering the developer's motives behind implementing this gamification strategy. Since one of their goals is to profit from the app, gamification through in-app shops, new items, and special collections also serves this purpose of increasing profitability, encouraging users to spend money or spend more time to watch advertisements within the apps. This highlights the need to discuss ethical concerns regarding gamification strategies, which will be explored further in the discussion section.

Furthermore, all three apps allow users to collaborate with other players (*Cooperation*) to accomplish a common goal: *Forest* provides the feature "Plant together", *Study Bunny* offers the feature "Study with friends" to promote group productivity, and *Focus Quest* adopts a cooperation element in the form of a group missions. Several user reviews from all apps indicated that these cooperative features helped foster productivity, however, it required improvement in its implementation. For instance, one *Study Bunny* user suggested that they would appreciate more if the app offered the ability to see each other's study situations while studying together (18 January 2024, *Study Bunny Reviews*), while a *Forest* user proposed a feature where multiple people can plant trees in the same garden to foster user collaboration (12 March 2024, *Forest reviews*).

In terms of the Fictional dimension and story-based strategies, user reviews indicate that integrating a story (*Narrative*) into the gamified experience can boost user engagement. This is particularly evident when the story fosters an emotional connection. The findings reveal that many *Study Bunny* users developed an attachment to the bunny, viewing it as a pet companion or even an extension of themselves. This emotional bond was strengthened by actions like purchasing items for the bunny, as one of the users expressed:

"I want to keep him happy, so I study hard. I'll do anything for my sweet little bun." (14 February 2024, *Study Bunny Reviews*).

Unlike *Focus Quest*, users are attracted to the unfolding story throughout the experience, ultimately making the focus session more enjoyable and motivating. For instance, one user review expressed that the inclusion of "exciting stories" helped them overcome previous feelings of boredom and stay focused on their lessons (29 June 2023, *Focus Quest reviews*). In addition, other user

feedback related to a narrative element indicates that a good story can help enhance the experience and make it more meaningful:

"[...] PLEASE READ THE STORY. IT'S SO GOOD. It touches a philosophical view of "positive nihilism" and really touches the intricacies and importance of TIME. [...]" (21 March 2024, *Focus Quest reviews*).

Even though user insights present several beneficial aspects of gamification mentioned above, they also reveal downsides associated with other strategies. One example is the implementation of *Economy* within the apps. The concept of a trading system can increase user's engagement but it can backfire if the system is designed in the way that allows users to make in-game purchases instead of encouraging them to collect more focus time. For instance, one reviewer of *Focus Quest* (6 September 2023, *Focus Quest reviews*), criticized a feature that allows players to purchase action points using diamonds, which turned the app into a "pay to win" game. In this sense, gamification detracted from the original goal of motivating users to engage in focused study sessions.

Moreover, the results reveal that there is a downside of adding too much storytelling elements into gamification, which can overshadow the primary app features designed to achieve the app's goal. This imbalance can become a distraction, making it more challenging for users to complete their tasks, as users of *Focus Quest* commented:

"There's no time to focus on work because it's basically focusing for 20 minutes and playing the game, collecting rewards, upgrades, and 1000 more things for 2 hours before i could focus again." (19 April 2024, *Focus Quest reviews*)

In summary, our analysis reveals diverse approaches to gamification within the examined apps, highlighting a deeper understanding of how users perceive and evaluate these different strategies in relation to their focus goals. These results set the stage for a critical discussion in the following section on how to improve gamification for enhancing focus, while also addressing potential drawbacks and ethical issues that need to be considered in the design.

5 DISCUSSION

In this section, we critically analyze the results and examine the integration of gamification to narrative-based focus apps and how it is aligned with users' expectations for achieving focus-oriented goals. We also look into the potential paradoxes related to gamification in focus apps, which raises questions on responsible usage and ethical concerns. Additionally, we highlight the value of story-based strategies in enhancing gamified experiences and discuss the technological considerations that should be addressed when designing gamified experiences within the context of focus apps. Simultaneously, we pinpoint areas where improvements can be made, and propose recommendations for the future development of gamified focus apps. Finally, we acknowledge the study's limitations and propose avenues for further research in this domain.

The findings highlight the distinct role of gamification in the examined focus apps. Gamification has been reported boosting engagement and motivation, but also carries the risk of distraction if not carefully integrated. Aligned with prior research [66],

our findings indicate that poorly designed gamification in the focus apps can distract users from focusing on their actual tasks. This emphasizes the need to find the right balance between gamification strategies and the core focus-enhancing goals of these apps. Therefore, it is worth initiating a discussion about the strategic use of gamification elements and emphasizing the need for further research in the future. Rather than seeking to implement every strategy erratically, we advocate for a selective approach that supports focus-related behaviors. We propose that each gamification element should be critically examined beforehand to ensure its relevance and alignment with the goal of the apps, not simply creating entertaining distractions. Moreover, due to the inherent tension between gamification and focus app goals, it is crucial to keep in mind that aiming solely for increasing user engagement does not translate to success in the context of focus apps. Such engagement happens within the apps, not guaranteeing the engagement of users' tasks outside of the app. To achieve focus-oriented goals, we propose that it is essential to explore alternative gamification strategies that can enhance meaningful gamification, helping users to find a deeper connection to the real-world context rather than attaching to features in the apps.

Based on the reviews, these focus apps seem to be helpful for people mostly in short-term usage. Nonetheless, examining the potential ethical dilemmas embedded within their design is critical. It is thus worth questioning whether gamification is the best tool for issues with attention and concentration [66], and scrutinizing the commercial motivations behind these apps is called for. As studies on narrative design (e.g., [8, 49]) as well as our findings show, fictional features and story-based strategies are often employed to evoke emotions and to engage users or players for continuous use of the product, however, using deliberate affectiveness or affective design may be questionable especially with the objective of concentration, as it may at worst promote addictive behavior [37]. Additionally, it cannot be denied that the commercial focus apps generate revenue based on how much people use them. The more time users spend within the app, the more potential for in-app purchases or ad views. This developers' goal of making a profit directly conflict with the users' desire for minimizing distractions. Ultimately, it can be seen as paradoxical in this design concept that there is a need for mobile apps to help you stop using other mobile apps [66].

Furthermore, the findings shed light on the value story-based strategies brings to gamified experiences. While traditional gamification elements (such as points, level, and progression) have proven effective in motivating users [21, 55], our study suggests that integrating a narrative can enhance user engagement and foster a deeper emotional connection. To elaborate further, story-based strategies in all three apps facilitated emotional attachment and encouraged engagement towards the in-app characters. User reviews indicated that this emotional attachment increased commitment, as the narrative consequences within the stories motivated users to focus and remain engaged with the app. In this sense, story provides a compelling reason for sustained participation, going beyond solely relying on extrinsic motivators [7]. However, in line with Järvelä et al. [36], our analysis of three cases shows that implementing story-based strategies within gamification can be a challenging task. Supporting

motivation and meaningful use is important for users to direct their attention better [1, 52], and our results suggest that including a meaningful story in a gamified app can continuously motivate users, however, the appropriate amount or breadth of story-based strategies is not straightforward. The examined reviews indicate that individual preferences could shape the effect on how much story content is beneficial. Some users found apps with very simple narratives, such as *Forest* and *Study Bunny*, engaging enough that it made them focus, whereas other users found following the highly engaging story of *Focus Quest* more helpful. In contrast, some users thought that *Focus Quest* had too many features, which distracted them from their original task. It could be that the right approach should be somewhat personalized, especially with something like attention and focus issues. This aligns with previous findings highlighting that users have different needs and approaches for focus apps [40] and their design needs to include freedom of choice and personalization [40, 50, 52]. Some of the apps had already approached this with settings where users can modify some of the core mechanics, such as being able to turn off the punishing mechanic of the dead tree in *Forest*, or the sad emotions of the bunny in *Study Bunny*. Enabling such settings may be beneficial, but eventually the success depends largely on the function of a story and how well it is integrated into gamification that ideally would provide a cohesive and gameful experience, which, ultimately, is a rather subjective experience [33]. Additionally, we recommend introducing a captivating narrative with a balance between engagement and simplicity. While incorporating characters, settings, and themes, it is essential to be mindful not to overwhelm users with excessive game content. One great example is the user reflection on the large amount of dialogues as seen in *Focus Quest*. Even though the unfolding story may enhance user engagement to continue collect focus time, the trade-off of providing excessive dialogue can lead to longer screen time, not on their tasks. By simplifying a narrative, it is worth to step back and review all story-based strategies, questioning its implementation by evaluating, for example, how does the storytelling impact the overall gameful experience and the apps' goals (e.g., too many characters), or are any of the elements unnecessarily complex (e.g., over-detailed backstory). As a result, this may ensure that the story complements the app's objective, which could enhance user engagement without causing distractions.

Lastly, the results draw attention to the technological aspect of online apps. While focus apps offer solutions for reducing smartphone distractions, their requirement for constant Internet connection presents challenges related to the overall gamified experience. The first challenge raised from the findings is accessibility. The continuous use of wireless networks for data syncing, updates, or content streaming can lead to high bandwidth usage and data consumption [53], which is problematic for users with limited data plans. According to users' reviews, we can see that limited connectivity hinders users' ability to access the app's features when needed, possibly leading to a decreased user engagement. Secondly, the constant Internet connection required can create potential interruptions and temptations from online notifications, which goes against the purpose of the app. Therefore, these issues highlight the necessity for an offline mode that aligns

with the core objective of focus apps. By eliminating the need to constantly connect to the Internet, an offline version can assist users in accessing the app without restrictions based on their network conditions, and can help them avoid distractions associated with online activities, thereby promoting a more focused work environment. Addressing these technological challenges is thus crucial for enhancing user experience and the effectiveness of gamification, particularly within the context of focus apps.

5.1 Limitations and directions for future research

This study has several limitations. While this study provides valuable insights into the use of gamification in narrative-based focus apps, it's important to note that the analysis was based on only three apps, which may not fully represent all gamified focus apps available in the market. Future research should aim to increase the sample size to include a wider variety of apps to enhance the robustness and applicability of the results. Secondly, data sources gathered in this study are limited. Due to the inclusion of only two data collection points, the study may not fully capture the diversity and complexity of the studied phenomena. Moreover, the research scope is focused solely on one review platform, the Google Play Store. This reliance on publicly available data potentially overlooks in-depth information obtainable from other sources, such as direct user interviews or surveys. Therefore, further studies are encouraged to expand on this study by incorporating a wider array of data. Thirdly, the use of online feedback introduces potential sample bias, as it primarily reflects engaged online users who are familiar with the review posting process and potentially excludes less active ones [31]. In addition, users with a very positive or negative experience with the product are more likely to write reviews than those with a moderate or neutral experience [34]. Also it should be noted that the data collection from Google Play Store may be influenced by recent feedback from users in the same region and using similar devices, provided by individuals with verified Google accounts based on their app experience, which could shape the nature of the feedback and thus our results. In addition, the data primarily reflects the experience of Android users. They may not adequately reflect feedback from users of other systems (e.g., iOS) and thus may be subject to the risk of a single perspective bias.

The results introduced in this paper are still tentative, thus we are seeking to expand and deepen the analysis in our upcoming work. Additionally, as research on focus apps is still in its infancy, we propose that further research is needed for the systematic evaluation of gamified focus apps' effectiveness by looking into different gamification strategies in different specific focus. Such line of study would further solidify the understanding of the potential benefits and optimal implementation of gamification in focus-enhancing applications. Moreover, further studies on the long-term consequences of gamification for sustained attention enhancement and the establishment of ethical design guidelines would be vital for the socially responsible advancement of gamified focus apps.

6 CONCLUSIONS

While focus apps, and more broadly productivity apps are widely used, there is not yet scientific evidence of their effectiveness. As

focus apps are occupying the middle ground between productivity and mobile health apps, there should be increased effort in understanding the contents and effectiveness of these apps. This paper aims to contribute to exploring the phenomenon of focus apps through the lens of gamification. Our study examined the integration of gamification with narrative-based focus apps, with a particular look on story-based strategies, analyzing how they are implemented to enhance user focus. We investigated user reviews to identify the perceived effectiveness of these elements from user perspective. The results of our analysis of three gamified focus apps, *Focus Quest*, *Forest*, and *Study Bunny*, indicate that different gamification strategies elicit varied emotional responses from users regarding their app experiences, both positive and negative, and their perception on whether the apps effectively support concentration on their tasks. While gamification can enhance user engagement and motivation, an excessive use or a poor integration can lead to distraction and frustration. As such, our findings emphasize the need to carefully balance gamification with the app's core focus-enhancing goals. Besides, the results highlight the need for ethical considerations while implementing gamification within focus apps and the strategic adoption of story-based strategies to align with user needs and preferences. Ultimately, this study is a step towards understanding how gamification can be harnessed for enhancing focus in the digital world. However, there are limitations to this study, including the limited scope of study and the potential of selection bias. To further solidify this study, we suggest that future research should explore systematic evaluation on systematic evaluation of gamified focus apps' effectiveness and delve deeper into motivations behind focus app usage and long-term effectiveness measures.

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